

THERMOSS

Advanced heating and cooling technologies for efficient thermal retrofitting to buildings

Fernando Centeno
Exergy Ltd

Goals of the project

The main goals of the project are to produce an outstanding contribution to the EU-wide deployment of advanced technologies for heating and cooling, enhance the energy efficiency of residential buildings and facilitate their connection to district heating and cooling networks. To do so, THERMOSS is ensuring an efficient match between supply and demand of energy through real-time management of thermal energy.

THERMOSS is increasing the efficiency of residential building thermal retrofitting through advanced heating and cooling technologies. It is also sharpening construction and energy industry awareness by providing open access to a heating and cooling technology database to promote the deployment of the most effective solutions. The project is also demonstrating a high potential of replication throughout Europe, allowing a large market introduction of the selected THERMOSS solutions before 2025.

THERMOSS solution

THERMOSS focuses on six main technologies installed alone, in combination, or with solar thermal panels. The electric heat pump (1) is the most common THERMOSS technology. It uses an electric motor to extract heat from the outside air and warm the house or hot water for the taps. Heat pumps have higher efficiency than conventional gas boilers, which only use the heat from gas combustion. Due to the lower price of gas compared with electricity, a convenient combination in most European countries is the hybrid version (2). The hybrid heat pump selects electricity or gas according to the COP (coefficient of performance)–

an indicator of efficiency that changes with external temperature. Another type of heat pump uses the absorption cycle. The gas absorption heat pump (3), uses gas as its source but generates heat more efficiently than a gas boiler can. The micro combined heat and power (CHP) unit with solid oxide fuel cell (4) uses gas to produce electricity and heat at the same time, saving the user from purchasing electricity from the grid, while also warming the home. These technologies are installed both in individually central heated buildings and district heating networks. For the latter case, the Heat Interface Unit (5) was deployed, providing a heat exchanger with higher control capabilities to reduce heat losses. The bi-directional substation (6) was designed for prosumers (producers and consumers of energy), enabling the exchange of heat in two directions. To be able to collect data and allow control of the system, a cloud platform for monitoring the data from the buildings was developed. Real-time optimisation algorithms and control strategies were also developed and deployed at the sites concurrently with the hardware.

Demonstration

After the laboratory tests, the technology and associated optimisation were deployed at four different locations (Southampton, Portsmouth, Riga and San Sebastian) to prove that THERMOSS solutions can be effectively applied to most buildings, leading to savings of up to 30% in primary energy consumption!

SUMMARY

Building and district Thermal Retrofit and Management Solutions.

THERMOSS is a research project which began in September 2016 and is funded by the European Commission Horizon 2020 programme. The THERMOSS project is based on the development of new innovative technologies and integrating them with control algorithms to reach 30% energy savings.

PROJECT LEAD PROFILES

Exergy Ltd is an environmental engineering and consultancy company delivering advanced solutions to facilitate the **transition to the circular economy**. Exergy collaborates with its clients to help them achieve their sustainability goals. Exergy excels at delivering holistic circular solutions to minimise (detrimental) environmental impacts while creating additional commercial value.

PROJECT PARTNERS

The THERMOSS project is based on the cooperation of 15 partners from eight European countries. The project consortium consists of industry leaders, SMEs, universities and other research institutions.

CONTACT DETAILS

Fernando Centeno
Exergy Ltd

 +44 (0) 24 7623 6151

 fernandocenteno@exergy.uk.com

 thermoss.eu

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